

Plan of analyses

Exposure to perchlorate, nitrate, and thiocyanate among pregnant women in Norway.

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1. Version log

Version no.	Date	Comments
0.1	September 19 th 2024	First draft, shared with writing group
0.2	November 22 nd 2024	Revised and shared with other co-authors.
0.3	February 26 th 2025	Added objective of assessing variation in repeated measures
1.0	March 10 th 2025	Final

2. Authorship

Roles	Responsibilities	Who
Writing group	Will be responsible for drafting the POA, performing the statistical analyses and make the first draft of the manuscript.	Kjersti S. Bakken (first author) Tor A. Strand Hans Krabbe Tim IM Korevaar
Other co-authors	Will give feedback on POA and results. Will also give input on content and feedback on manuscript.	Ingunn T. Fauskrud Robin Baan Jan Ludvig Lyche Bjørn Gunnar Nedrebø Robin P Peeters Siri Kaldenbach Beate S. Solvik

3. Rationale for the study

Maternal thyroid hormones are vital for the developing fetus and maternal thyroid dysfunctions in pregnancy can lead to neurodevelopmental delays for the child. Iodine is an essential component of thyroid hormone. The anions perchlorate, thiocyanate and nitrate are ubiquitous environmental contaminants that competitively inhibit the uptake of iodine into the thyroid gland by the sodium-iodide symporter (NIS). At present, the human exposure to perchlorate, thiocyanate, and nitrate in Norway have not been quantified.

4. Aim and objectives

Aim:

Describe pregnant women's exposure to perchlorate, thiocyanate, and nitrate in Norway and explore determinants of urinary concentrations.

Objectives:

- 1) Describe the urinary concentrations of perchlorate, thiocyanate, and nitrate (N=197).
- 2) Describe variation in urinary concentrations of perchlorate, thiocyanate, and nitrate in two repeated measurements (N=53).
- 3) Explore possible determinants of urinary concentrations of perchlorate, thiocyanate, and nitrate (N=197).

5. Data source

We will use data from the mother and child health registry and the general research biobank at Innlandet Hospital Trust; Innlandet Health registry for Offspring and Parents (IHOP) and MoBI-biobank. Data for IHOP and MoBI-biobank is obtained from several different sources, including patient health records, patient reported data, and data from primary healthcare and public health clinics in Innlandet. We will include individuals who have consented to the registry and biobank and who have had their pregnancy urine samples analyzed for perchlorate, thiocyanate, and nitrate. The inclusion period is from 01.12.2021 to 31.08.2023. Total number of individuals included is 197 women. Of these women, 53 had two samples and 81 have also answered a small food frequency questionnaire (FFQ) during pregnancy.

6. Ethical considerations

IHOP and MoBI-biobank is consent-based. Ethical approval of the biobank has been granted by the Regional Ethical Committee for Health Research South-East A with the reference number 403616. The registry has also been approved by the hospitals Data Protection Officer with the reference number 23021676.

7. Outcome variables

- Urinary perchlorate concentration (ug/L), and adjusted for urinary creatinine (mmol)
- Urinary thiocyanate concentration (ug/L), and adjusted for urinary creatinine (mmol)
- Urinary nitrate concentration (mg/L), and adjusted for urinary creatinine (mmol)

8. Other variables

We will include descriptive variables and possible predictors.

From patient health records (on all):

- Maternal age (in years)
- Parity (in numbers)
- Smoking habits before pregnancy (yes, no never, no not now, unknown)
- Smoking habits during pregnancy (yes, no never, no not now, unknown)
- Snuff habits before pregnancy (yes, no never, no not now, unknown)
- Snuff habits during pregnancy (yes, no never, no not now, unknown)
- Use of multivitamin supplements before pregnancy (yes, no, unknown)
- Use of multivitamin supplements during pregnancy (yes, no, unknown)
- Use of other dietary supplements before pregnancy (yes, no, unknown)
- Use of other dietary supplements during pregnancy (yes, no, unknown)
- Gestational age at urine sampling (in days)
- Body Mass Index (kg/m²) pre-pregnancy
- Maternal education level (≤ 13 , 14-17, >17 years)
- Marital status (married/co-habitant, single/divorced/widow)
- Location (the municipality in which they live, categorized into areas or urban/rural)

From FFQ (on a subgroup):

- Intake of fatty fish, lean fish, red meat, white meat, dairy products, eggs, vegetables, fruits the last 14 days of answering the FFQ.

- Dietary habits (vegan, vegetarian, pesco-vegetarian, no restrictions, other)

9. Statistical analyses

We will use STATA 18.5 for the statistical analyses.

- Objective 1): Describe median, IQR, and range of urinary concentrations of perchlorate, thiocyanate, and nitrate, adjusted for creatinine.
- Objective 2): Assess intraclass correlation in urinary concentrations of perchlorate, thiocyanate, and nitrate, adjusted for creatinine, between repeated samples using one-way analysis of variance.
- Objective 3): Explore determinants for concentrations using multiple regression models where the method will be decided based on the distribution of the outcome variables. We will explore all the variables described in point 8. We will also consider generating plots depicting the association between some of the determinants and the outcomes.

10. Planned tables and figures

Table 1. Study population characteristics (N=197)

	Median (IQR) or N (%)
Maternal age in years	00 (00–00)
Parity	
0	00 (0.0)
1	00 (0.0)
2+	00 (0.0)
Gestational age at urine sampling (days)	000 (00–000)
Smoking during pregnancy	
Yes	00 (0.0)
No, not now	00 (0.0)
No, never	00 (0.0)
Snuff use during pregnancy	
Yes	00 (0.0)
No, not now	00 (0.0)
No, never	00 (0.0)
Use of multivitamin supplements before pregnancy; yes	00 (0.0)
Use of multivitamin supplements during pregnancy; yes	00 (0.0)
Use of other dietary supplements during pregnancy; yes	00 (0.0)
Iron	00 (0.0)
Iodine	00 (0.0)
Omega-3	00 (0.0)
Body mass index (kg/m ²)	00.0 (00–00)
Educational level	
Finished High School (≤13 years)	00 (0.0)
Higher education less than 4 years (14–17 years)	00 (0.0)
Higher education 4 years or more (17+ years)	00 (0.0)
Marital status	
Married/co-habitant	00 (0.0)
Single/divorced/widowed	00 (0.0)

Table 2. Food intake in pregnancy (N=82)

	N (%)
Fatty fish	
No fatty fish intake	00 (0.0)
Low intake; less than 2 meals per week	00 (0.0)
High intake; 2 or more meals per week	00 (0.0)
Lean fish	
No lean fish intake	00 (0.0)
Low intake; less than 2 meals per week	00 (0.0)
High intake; 2 or more meals per week	00 (0.0)
Red meat	
No red meat intake	00 (0.0)
Low intake; less than 2 meals per week	00 (0.0)
High intake; 2 or more meals per week	00 (0.0)
White meat	
No white meat intake	00 (0.0)
Low intake; less than 2 meals per week	00 (0.0)
High intake; 2 or more meals per week	00 (0.0)
Dairy products; g	00 (0.0)
No dairy intake	00 (0.0)
Low intake; less than 2 portions per week	00 (0.0)
Medium intake; less than 3 portions per week	00 (0.0)
High intake; 3 or more portions per week	00 (0.0)
Eggs; g	
No egg intake	00 (0.0)
Low intake; less than 2 meals per week	00 (0.0)
High intake; 2 or more meals per week	00 (0.0)
Vegetables	
Low intake; 1-3 meals per week	00 (0.0)
High intake; more than 3 meals per week	00 (0.0)
Fruits	
Low intake; 1-3 meals per week	00 (0.0)
High intake; more than 3 meals per week	00 (0.0)
Dietary habits	
Vegan	-
Vegetarian (and pesco-vegetarian)	-

Table 3. Median and range of values of urine concentrations of NIS-inhibitors, adjusted for creatinine, measured in pregnancy in Norway. N = 197

	Median	Range (min–max or IQR)
Perchlorate (µg/L)	000.000	000.000–000.000
Thiocyanate (µg/L)	000.000	000.000–000.000
Nitrate (mg/L)	000.000	000.000–000.000

Table 4. Intraclass correlation of urine concentrations of NIS-inhibitors, adjusted for creatinine, measured two times in pregnancy in Norway. N = 53

	One-way analysis of variance		Bland-Altman	
	ICC	95% CI	Average difference	95% CI
Perchlorate (µg/L)	0.00	0.00 – 0.00	0.00	0.00 – 0.00
Thiocyanate (µg/L)	0.00	0.00 – 0.00	0.00	0.00 – 0.00
Nitrate (mg/L)	0.00	0.00 – 0.00	0.00	0.00 – 0.00

In Table 5 we will include variables from Table 1 and 2 which are associated with the levels of NIS-inhibitors.

Table 5. Possible determinants for concentration of NIS-inhibitors measured in pregnancy in Norway. N = 197

Predictors	Perchlorate		Thiocyanate		Nitrate	
	Crude (95% CI)	Adjusted (95% CI)	Crude (95% CI)	Adjusted (95% CI)	Crude (95% CI)	Adjusted (95% CI)
Variable	0.0 (0.0–0.0)	0.0 (0.0–0.0)	0.0 (0.0–0.0)	0.0 (0.0–0.0)	0.0 (0.0–0.0)	0.0 (0.0–0.0)